

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds : Part-I. Synthesis of 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-5-phenyl-4-(substituted-sulphonamidobenzeneazo) pyrazoles and Evaluation of their Antibacterial Properties.

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I-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones on condensation with hydrazine hydrate (100%), phenylhydrazine, *p*-toluylhydrazine, and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine give the corresponding N¹-substituted-3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-5-phenyl-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) pyrazoles. The antibacterial properties of all these pyrazole derivatives have been tested by the cup-plate agar diffusion method against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*.

PYRAZOLE derivatives have during recent times acquired considerable importance because of their use as therapeutics¹⁻¹⁸; amongst the more recent applications, some of these find use in fight against cancer.^{19,20} Some pyrazole derivatives have also been reported to occur in nature^{21,22}, and 3-*n*-nonylpyrazole isolated from "Houttuynia cordata", a plant of piperaceae family from tropical Asia was found to inhibit the growth of *S. aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Trichophyton*, *Zygosaccharomyces salus* and *Aspergillus niger*.

Pyrazoles having sulphonamide moiety attached at different positions have been synthesised and reported to be active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*,²³⁻²⁸ and N¹-(1-phenylpyrazolyl) sulphanilamide (Orisul) has been found to be therapeutically active and this is now being commonly used in medicine. Very recently, the synthesis of some pyrazoles having arylazo grouping at position-4 have been reported and found to exhibit activity.²⁹

Although pyrazoles having a sulphonamide moiety, an azo-linkage and azo compounds of sulphonamides individually possess interesting pharmacological properties, yet hardly any work has been reported on the synthesis of pyrazoles having a sulphonamide moiety attached through an azo-linkage. It was therefore, thought of interest to synthesise compounds possessing all the above three moieties in one system and screen these *in vitro* for their pharmacological properties.

The azo compounds required for this work were prepared by coupling diazotised sulphonamide bases with 1-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-3-phenyl propane-1,3-dione in presence of sodium acetate.³⁰

The present communication describes the synthesis of N¹-substituted-3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-5-phenyl-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) pyrazoles of the type I. These were obtained by condensing 1,3-diaryl-2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones with hydrazine hydrate (100%), phenylhydrazine, *p*-toluylhydrazine and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine. The homogeneity of these was tested through T. L. C. using benzene-methanol mixture (45:5) as the solvent system. This structure was assigned on the basis of the findings of earlier workers^{31,32} and characterisation of these was done through I.R. spectra and elemental analysis.

The different compounds synthesised and the results of their screening are entered in Tables 1 to 4.

The antibacterial properties were studied at two different concentrations of 500 μ g/ml and 1000 μ g/ml and the results with dilution of 500 μ g/ml have been entered in the Tables.

Our findings indicate that all the pyrazole derivatives exhibited considerable activity against *E. coli* and were inactive against *S. aureus* except compounds number 9 in Table 1 and 7 in Table 4 which showed very meagre activity.

TABLE 1—3-(*p*-METHOXYPHENYL)-5-PHENYL-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES
(I, R = H)

S. No.	R ₁	M. P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Mol. formula	% Found		Reqd.		Antibacterial activity against	
						C	H	C	H	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	246-7	ORN	69	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₅ S	61.1	4.6	61.0	4.4	(-)	(+)
2.	Acetyl	246-7	BOF	69	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₅ S	60.5	4.5	60.6	4.4	(-)	(+)
3.	Phenyl	211-2	SRN	63	C ₂₉ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₅ S	65.8	4.6	66.0	4.5	(-)	(+)
4.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	236-7	BOF	66	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₅ SCl	61.7	4.0	61.8	4.0	(-)	(++)
5.	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	230	SRF	61	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₅ S	66.3	4.9	66.5	4.8	(-)	(+)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	220	OF	64	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₅ S	64.7	4.6	64.6	4.6	(-)	(+)
7.	Pyrimidyl	290	R	67	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₇ S	60.9	4.3	61.0	4.1	(-)	(+)
8.	Guanidyl	278	O	63	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₇ S	57.9	4.5	58.1	4.4	(-)	(+)
9.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	146	SR	64	C ₂₈ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₇ S	62.4	4.7	62.3	4.6	(+)	(-)

TABLE 2—1,5-DIPHENYL-3-(P-METHOXYPHENYL)-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

S. No.	R ₁	M. P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Mol. formula	Found %		Reqd.		Antibacterial activity against	
						I, R=C ₆ H ₅)	C	H	C	H	S. aureus
1.	H	247-8	BR	70	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₅ S	66.1	4.5	66.0	4.5	(-)	(+)
2.	Acetyl	242	BR	68	C ₃₀ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₅ S	65.5	4.4	65.3	4.5	(-)	(++)
3.	Phenyl	190-1	BO	63	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₅ S	69.7	4.6	69.7	4.6	(-)	(++)
4.	p-Chlorophenyl	235	BR	65	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₅ SCl	66.0	4.1	65.8	4.2	(-)	(++)
5.	p-Methylphenyl	245-6	BO	62	C ₃₅ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₅ S	70.3	4.9	70.1	4.8	(-)	(++)
6.	p-Methoxyphenyl	234-5	BR	64	C ₃₅ H ₂₉ O ₄ N ₅ S	68.2	4.9	68.3	4.7	(-)	(+)
7.	Pyrimidyl	285	SR	66	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₇ S	65.6	4.3	65.4	4.2	(-)	(+)
8.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	196	SON	62	C ₃₄ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₇ S	66.1	4.6	66.3	4.7	(-)	(++)

TABLE 3—1-(P-METHYLPHENYL)-3-(P-METHOXYPHENYL)-5-PHENYL-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

S. No.	R ₁	M. P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Mol. formula	Found %		Reqd.		Antibacterial activity against	
						I, R=p-CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄)	C	H	C	H	S. aureus
1.	H	205	SON	56	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₅ S	66.7	4.7	66.5	4.8	(-)	(++)
2.	Acetyl	186	SORF	56	C ₃₁ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₅ S	66.0	4.6	65.8	4.7	(-)	(+)
3.	Phenyl	188	SOF	49	C ₃₅ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₅ S	70.0	4.9	70.1	4.8	(-)	(++)
4.	p-Chlorophenyl	216	R	50	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₅ SCl	66.5	4.2	66.3	4.4	(-)	(+)
5.	p-Methylphenyl	226	RO	49	C ₃₆ H ₃₁ O ₃ N ₅ S	70.3	5.0	70.5	5.0	(-)	(++)
6.	p-Methoxyphenyl	230	SO	51	C ₃₆ H ₃₁ O ₄ N ₅ S	68.8	4.8	68.7	4.9	(-)	(++)
7.	Pyrimidyl	255-6	BrR	54	C ₃₆ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₇ S	66.1	4.2	65.9	4.5	(-)	(++)

TABLE 4—1-(P-NITROPHENYL)-3-(P-METHOXYPHENYL)-5-PHENYL-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

S. No.	R ₁	M. P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Mol. formula	Found %		Reqd.		Antibacterial activity against	
						I, R=p-NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₄)	C	H	C	H	S. aureus
1.	H	254-5	SDR	74	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₆ S	60.6	4.0	60.6	4.0	(-)	(++)
2.	Acetyl	259	SR	74	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₆ S	60.4	4.2	60.4	4.0	(-)	(++)
3.	Phenyl	228	OF	70	C ₃₄ H ₂₈ O ₅ N ₆ S	64.6	4.2	64.8	4.1	(-)	(+)
4.	p-Chlorophenyl	217	O	72	C ₃₄ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₆ SCl	61.5	3.5	61.4	3.8	(-)	(+)
5.	p-Methylphenyl	197-8	SROF	68	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₅ N ₆ S	65.0	4.3	65.2	4.3	(-)	(+)
6.	p-Methoxyphenyl	238	SRF	71	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₆ N ₆ S	63.5	4.2	63.6	4.2	(-)	(+)
7.	Pyrimidyl	276	DR	74	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S	60.8	3.9	60.7	3.8	(+)	(++)

B=Bright, Br=Brownish, D=Dark, F=Flakes, G=Golden, L=Light, N=Needles, O=Orange, P=Pale, R=Red, S=Shining, Y=Yellow, and W=White.

Experimental

3-(p-Methoxyphenyl)-5-phenyl-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) pyrazoles.

The azo compound, 1-(p-methoxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) propane-1,3-dione (0.1 g) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid, hydrazine hydrate (100%; 0.05 g) was added and the contents refluxed in an oil-bath at 160°-80°. To the cooled solution, few drops of water were added and the reaction mixture left overnight. The deposited product was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from glacial acetic acid or ethanol-glacial acetic acid or ethanol-DMF mixture.

Pyrazoles from p-toluyhydrazine were prepared by employing the above procedure.

However, reactions with phenylhydrazine were carried out in glacial acetic acid-ethanol mixture by refluxing on a water bath and in the case of p-nitrophenylhydrazine, addition of a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid was found essential.

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